

ROLE OF GREEN CHEMISTRY IN QUALITATIVE PHARMACEUTICALS

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ABSTRACT

Green chemistry is a good approach to the design, manufacture and the use of chemical substances in the production of qualitative pharmaceutical products to intentionally reduce or eliminate the hazardous substances. It mainly focuses on reduction, recycling or elimination of the use of toxic and hazardous chemicals in the production of pharmaceutical products processes by finding creative, alternative routes for making the desired products that minimize the impact on environment. This paper provides an overview of application of 12 principles and future trends of green chemistry. Green or sustainable chemistry is a term that refers to the creation of chemical products and process that reduce or eliminate the use and production of harmful substances. In this green chemistry they are used chemical substances or chemical process that does not have negative impact on environment. It is based on twelve principles that can be

used to initially create or recreate molecules, materials, reactions and process that are safer to environment. This article shows examples of the prevailing trends in ways that green chemistry reduces the impact of chemical processes on the environment.

KEYWORDS: Green synthesis, solvents, hazardous chemicals.

GREEN CHEMISTRY

Introduction

Green chemistry is the design of chemical products and processes that reduce or eliminate the use or regeneration of hazardous substances. Green chemistry applies across the life cycle of a chemical product, including its design, manufacture and its disposal.^[1]

Green chemistry plays a crucial role in pharmaceutical analysis by promoting the development and implementation of environmentally friendly methods for drug synthesis, analysis and quality control. It aims to minimize the use of hazardous substances and reduce waste generation leading to safer and more sustainable pharmaceutical practices.^[2]

The pharmaceutical industry is most leading contributor to the world's health with pharmaceutical products. These pharmaceutical products playing major role in fighting, controlling and preventing diseases the world.^[3] Manufacturing of pharmaceutical products is deeply resource intensive, with the need for raw materials extraction, the handling of harmful solvents, and the mass flow of chemical waste. Many pharmaceutical processes are based on the use of non renewable sources i.e., petrochemicals and require toxic solvents that present an environmental and human threat. Manufacturing of waste products including harmful byproducts and not only jeopardizes the air, water and soil but accumulates heavy weight on waste management system.

Green chemistry is a science based philosophy in which contains designing chemicals products and processes with the main intention of making pharmaceutical products are less hazardous and more sustainable. Now a day's science and technology is going more advanced progress in economic development, it leads to environmental degradation which is manifested by climatic change, the issue of ozone holes.

The use of green chemistry in pharmaceutical synthesis is a most important in research and practice. By using the principles of green chemistry harmonizing the pharmaceutical products, the pharmaceutical industry can curtail its dependence on toxic reagents reduce waste product generation and restrain energy consumption while still sustaining a high level of drug safety and efficacy.

APPLICATIONS OF GREEN CHEMISTRY IN SYNTHESIS OF PHARMACEUTICAL PRODUCTS

Reduces pollution

Green chemistry in pharmacy reduces the use of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in the synthesis of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), minimizing air pollution. Example: using water as a solvent instead of VOCs in the synthesis of ibuprofen.^[4]

➤ Traditional synthesis of ibuprofen:

Ibuprofen synthesis using VOCs (e.g. dichloromethane)

➤ 4-Isobutylacetophenone + CH₂Cl₂ → 4-Isobutylacetophenone-Cl

➤ 4-Isobutylacetophenone-Cl + NaOH → Ibuprofen

➤ time : 14-24 hours

Green chemistry synthesis:

Ibuprofen synthesis using water as a solvent (At 50-60⁰)

14-Isobutylacetophenone + H₂O → 4-Isobutylacetophenone - H₂O

4-Isobutylacetophenone-H₂O + NaOH → Ibuprofen

Time:2-6 hours

2. Conserve resources

Utilizing a one pot synthesis reaction to produce an API minimizing the need for multiple reactions and reducing solvent usage.^[4]

IN one pot synthesis, all reactants are combined in a single reaction vessel, eliminating the need for multiple reactants and reducing solvent usage

3. Saves energy

Green chemistry in pharmacy reduces energy consumption in manufacturing process.

Example: Using microwave –assisted synthesis to reduce reaction times and energy required for API synthesis.^[4]

4. Promotes sustainability

Green chemistry in pharmacy enables the development of sustainable pharmaceutical products.

Example: Designing biodegradable drug delivery systems to reduce environmental impact.⁴

5. Reduce waste

Green chemistry in pharmacy minimizes waste generation in pharmaceutical manufacturing.^[5]

Example: Implementing a zero waste policy in API synthesis, where all by- products are recycled or re used. i.e., zero waste synthesis of paracetamol (acetaminophene).

Impact of 12 Principles of green chemistry in Qualitative pharmaceuticals:

There are twelve principles of green chemistry have been developed by Paul anastas and John Warner of EPA and their green chemistry theory and practice book 1998, they explained their meaning in practice.^[6]

The principles of green chemistry explains about the reduction of removal of dangerous or harmful substances from the syntesis, production and application of chemical products and the substances which are harmful to human health and environment those substances are removed or eliminated. While going in green chemistry process, it is impossible to meet the requirements of all twelve principles of the process at the same time, but it try to attempts to apply as many principles as possible during the synthesis of pharmaceutical products.

Green chemistry is ecologically harmless and this sustainable chemistry is the manufacture and application of chemical products and process that reduce or eliminate the use of hazardous substances during production of qualitative pharmaceuticals.

1. Prevent waste
2. Maximize atom economy
3. Less hazardous chemical synthesis
4. Safer chemicals and products
5. Safer solvents and reaction conditions
6. Increases energy efficiency
7. Use renewable feed stocks
8. Avoid chemical derivatives
9. Use catalysts
10. Design for degradation after use
11. Analysis in real time to prevent pollution
12. Minimize potential for accidents

1. Prevention of waste

In pharmaceutical industries nearly 80%of waste in the pharmaceutical industry is associated with solvents and that about 60% of their energy is consumed, the solution is to reduce the use of solvents.^[7]

A good example is the new “green” production process of sertraline an anti depressant drug by which the introduction of ethanol as the sole solvent eliminates the need for the use,

distillation and recovery of four solvents (methylene chloride, THF, Toluene and Hexanes) resulting in a reduction in solvent composition of 250 to 25 liters per kg of sertraline.

2. Atom economy

Synthetic methods should be designed to maximize the incorporation of all materials used in the process into the final product. There is a known progress in the synthesis of ibuprofen. The main problem of old synthesis (boots process) is low economic cost, because the utilization of input raw materials is only about 40%.^[8]

In the 1990s a new green method of ibuprofen synthesis was developed involving only three steps, and almost all transitional materials are converted to the product (up to 99%) or regenerated and returned in the process and almost eliminated the generation of waste materials and this is one of the process of “green synthesis” shows a comparative comparison of classic boots and the “green” Hoechst synthesis of ibuprofen.

The E-factor is used to compare the process of comparing the proportions of waste materials and the desired product.

The calculation of E- factor is determined by the ratio of mass of waste (kg) per unit of product in kilograms.

$$\text{E-factor} = \text{kg of waste} / \text{kg of product}$$

3. Less Hazardous chemical synthesis

Replacing harmful chemicals with biological enzymes makes many industrial processes cleaner and cheaper. For Example: Traditional synthesis of Aspartane (Artificial Sweetener). In the enzyme catalyzed synthesis, the harmful chemicals (hydrochloric acid and methanol) are replaced by a biological enzyme (Thermolysin) making the process cleaner and cheaper.^[9]

The enzyme catalyzes the reaction under mild conditions, reducing the risk of hazardous by-products and waste.^[10]

Benefits

- *Reduced toxicity and corrosiveness
- *Lower environmental impact
- *Improved safety and handling
- *Cost saving through reduced waste and energy consumption.

4. Designing safer chemicals

The principle is used in the development of new insecticides and pesticides that are specific to target organisms, i.e., they are toxic only to target organisms and decompose into environmentally harmless substances.^[11]

Chloropyrifos is an insecticide toxic to beneficial insects and humans.

Chloropyrifos + Water → toxic metabolites

Designed Safer chemical: Pyrethrin (Target specific biodegradable)

Pyrethrin + Water → Harmless metabolites

Pyrethrin is designed as safer chemical that:

1. Targets only specific pests (e.g., Mosquitoes, moths)
2. It is target only to target organisms.
3. Decomposes into environmentally harmless substances (e.g., 3-phenoxybenzoic acid, chrysanthemic acid)

5. Safer Solvents and auxiliaries

The use of auxiliary substances (solvents, separation agents etc) should be made unnecessary whenever possible and when used as harm less solvents.^[12] The most preferred safer solvents as Water, Acetone, ethano, 2-propanol, 1-propanol, ethyl acetate hydropropyl acetate, methanol, methyl ethyl ketone, 1-butanol.

6. Design for energy efficiency

Energy requirements in a reaction should be minimized, synthetic methods should be conducted at ambient temperature and pressure. During chemical synthesis, the energy requirements should be minimum.^[13]

If Starting materials and reagents in a reaction mixture has to be heated to reflux for a required time, the time required has to kept for minimum for the minimum usage of energy.^[14]

Use of a catalyst has the great advantage of lowering the energy requirement of a reaction.

If the final product is impure, it has to purified by distillation, recrystallization, Ultrafiltration-for all this steps energy required.

By designing the process there is no need of separation and purification.

7. Use of renewable feed stocks

A raw material or feed stock should be renewable rather than depleting whenever technically and economically practical. For example production of poly lactic acid (PLA) from corn starch.^[15]

In this example a corn starch is a renewable feed stock, is converted into glucose through fermentation. The glucose is then fermented into lactic acid which is subsequently polymerized into poly lactic acid, a biodegradable product.

8. Reduce Derivatives

Unnecessary derivatization (Blocking group, protection and deprotection, temporary modification of physical or chemical process) should be avoided whenever possible.^[16]

Example: Production of antibiotics.

The production antibiotics are based on penicillin or replacement of classical chemical enzymatic process whereby 6-aminopenicillic acid is obtained by reacting with catalyzed immobilized enzyme penicillin amide.

This resulted in several chemical steps being replace by enzymatic reaction and no longer time required as low temperature, organic solvents, and completely unsuitable conditions that increased and complicated production in case of chemical synthesis.

9. Catalysis

Catalytic reagents are superior to stoichiometric reagents. In order to protect the environment, the catalysis principle promotes the biodegradable catalysts, which imply less energy use, avoiding the use of organo chlorine compounds and reducing the use of water or less waste water.^[17]

10. Design for degradation

Chemical products should be designed so that end of their function do not persist in the environment and instead they break down into harmless degradation products.^[18]

- Products designed should be biodegradable.
- During degradation the products themselves should not possess any toxic effects or be harmful to human health.

- It is possible to have a molecule which may possess functional groups that facilitate it for biodegradation.

The functional groups should be susceptible to hydrolysis, photolysis or other cleavage.

11. Real time analysis for pollution prevention

Analytical methodologies need to further developed to allow for real time, in process monitoring and control prior to the formation of hazardous substances.^[19]

- Analytical methodologies should be designed, so that they require minimum usage chemical, like recycling of some unreacted chemicals for the completion of reaction.
- Placement of sensors to monitor the generation of hazardous products
- During chemical reaction is also advantageous.
- Real time analysis for chemist is the process of “checking the process of chemical reaction as it happens”.

12. Inherently safer chemistry for accident prevention

Substance and the form of a substance used in chemical process should be chosen as to minimize the potential for chemical accidents, including releases, explosions and fires.

The hazards posed by toxicity, explosion, fire etc might be looked into and manufacturing plants should be so designed to eliminate the possibility of accidents.^[20]

CONCLUSION

The challenges being perceived in application of green and sustainable chemistry needs a wide variety adressal.

Particularly training on basic level of green chemistry which is designed to give a good basis in key concepts of process excellence in design, biocatalysis, selection of solvents, reagents tools and operational excellence.

Currently green chemisstry has impotence in the global stage.

Green chemistry will solve many environmental issues, it also generates quality products with minimum residues of toxic materials.

The primary goal of each pharmaceutical industry is to generate mony from available available raw materials and basic capital within sustainable industrial activities. Sustainable

industrial activities must meet today's needs without jeopardizing the needs of future generations, meaning that chemical processes need to use raw materials, water and energy in a way that does not harm the environment and be economically viable. Green chemistry, establishing a balance in the use of natural resources, economic growth and environmental conservation is possible. The application of the concept of green chemistry that introduces chemical safety implies adequate legal support through the regulation of certain procedures and activities that are unavoidable for the implementation of such a concept.

The concept of green chemistry is based on twelve principles that explain about reducing or eliminating hazardous or harmful substances from the synthesis, production and application of chemical products and thus the use of substances that are hazardous to human health and environment are reduced.

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